

Deep-ROCS: From speckle patterns to superior-resolved images by deep learning in Rotating Coherent Scattering Microscopy

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Abstract: Rotating coherent scattering (ROCS) microscopy is a label-free imaging technique that overcomes the optical diffraction limit by adding up the scattered laser light from a sample obliquely illuminated from different angles. Although ROCS imaging achieves 150 nm spatial and 10 ms temporal resolution, simply summing different speckle patterns may cause loss of sample information. In this paper we present Deep-ROCS, a neural network-based technique that generates a superior-resolved image by efficient numerical combination of a set of differently illuminated images. We show that Deep-ROCS can reconstruct super-resolved images more accurately than conventional ROCS microscopy, retrieving high-frequency information from a small number (6) of speckle images. We demonstrate the performance of Deep-ROCS experimentally on 200 nm beads and by computer simulations, where we show its potential for even more complex structures such as filament network.

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1. Introduction

In conventional (wide-field) optical microscopy the resolution is bounded by the diffraction limit, given by approximately half the wavelength of the light¹. Since the size of many biological structures is below this typical limit of 200 nm - 300 nm for visible light, numerous methods have been developed to surpass this limit, which typically rely on a combination of fluorescent-labeling with scanning or combining multiple diffraction limited images².

Fluorescence based super-resolution techniques enjoy the fundamental advantages of specificity and excellent contrast associated with all fluorescence microscopy, however they also suffer from the need to label the data with fluorophores, requiring a biochemical preparation method which increases experimental complexity. Additionally, these methods suffer from a limited photon emission thereby reducing temporal resolution, but also from photobleaching, which limits the applicable observation duration and possibly the resolution².

A label-free method allowing to surpass the diffraction limit without losing much of the temporal resolution would be highly desirable. One method developed to address this need uses rotating coherent scattering (ROCS)³⁻⁵. In this method, oblique sample illumination with coherent collimated light (usually in Total internal reflection dark field regime – TIR DF) is used, to capture images of the sample with the laser beam sweeping around the optical axis.

Thus, images are obtained at a high polar angle with different azimuthal illumination angles $\phi = 0, \dots, 2\pi$ (Figures 1a, 1b). It was demonstrated empirically and theoretically⁶ that similarly to Structured Illumination Microscopy^{6,7}, the oblique polar illumination can be viewed as a shift of the object's spatial spectrum relative to the optical transfer of the imaging system. Therefore, each image encodes information on frequencies beyond the diffraction limit, and

the challenge is to find the best way to combine this information into a single super-resolved image.

Figure 1: (a) Experimental realization of ROCS microscopy. Top view: a collimated 405 nm laser beam illuminates objects (beads) sequentially from all azimuthal directions, and light is scattered accordingly. Side view: The focused laser beam is scanned along a circle with azimuthal angle ϕ in the back focal plane (BFP) of a 1.46 NA objective lens. The object on the coverslip (CS) is illuminated by an oblique plane wave, which is totally internal reflected (TIR-Mode), given that the polar illumination angle exceeds the critical angle of total internal reflection. The scattered light is transferred to the camera, whereas the reflected beam is blocked in dark field imaging mode. (b) For each angle ϕ , a coherent image with many artefacts is generated, as shown for an arrangement of $2R = 200$ nm beads and three arbitrary directions. The final ROCS image (lower right) results from superposition of many different coherent images from all azimuthal directions $\phi = 0, \dots, 2\pi$. The increased spatial resolution of ROCS microscopy enables the separation of adjacent beads, which is not possible in conventional TIRF microscopy (lower left). Scale bar = 800 nm.

In ROCS microscopy, an image is generated by subsequent oblique illumination (polar angle $\theta = 70^\circ$) of the structure from all azimuthal directions $\phi = 0, \dots, 2\pi$. Currently, ROCS achieves 150 nm spatial and 10 ms temporal resolution without fluorophore bleaching and is therefore highly beneficial for live-cell imaging⁴. The camera image (in dark-field mode) therefore consists of the summation of images from all oblique illumination directions (ϕ_i, θ) , where an intensity image from a single direction ϕ can be described by:

$$p_{SD}(x, y, \phi) = |E_{cam}(x, y, \phi)|^2 = \left| \left[E_0 \cdot e^{-ik_i(\phi) \cdot r} \cdot f(x, y) \right] * PSF(x, y) \right|^2 \quad (1)$$

Here E_{cam} is the electric field pattern at the camera, $E_0 \cdot e^{-ik_i(\phi) \cdot r}$ is the electric field of the illumination beam coming from direction ϕ , k_i is the wave vector determined by the two illumination angles θ, ϕ_i , $f(x, y)$ is the object distribution, described by refractive index changes, $PSF(x, y, NA)$ is the coherent point spread function of the optical system and $*$ is the 2D convolution operator. Overall, ROCS can be described mathematically as the 2π integral or approximately the sum over N coherent images (eq. 2) from different illumination angles ϕ :

$$p_{ROCS}(x, y) = \int_0^{2\pi} |E_{cam}(x, y, \phi)|^2 d\phi \approx \sum_{n=1}^N |E_{cam}(x, y, \phi)|^2 \quad (2)$$

It turns out that a summation of $N = 36$ distinct images provides nearly the same image quality as from $N = 72$ images or as from the 2π continuous angular sweep. However, accumulating all

differently illuminated images into a single camera frame does not allow to retrieve the object's phase information $\varphi_{cam}(x, y, \phi)$ and other relevant Fourier (power) spectral components⁸:

$$P_{SD}(k_x, k_y, \phi) = |FT[E_{cam}(x, y, \phi)]|^2 \neq \tilde{I}(k_x, k_y, \phi) = FT[|E_{cam}(x, y, \phi)|^2] \quad (3)$$

Here, a minimum number N of raw images $p_{SD}(x, y, \phi)$ would be helpful to get access to this additional image information, without losing the advantage of fast image acquisition.

A new rising factor in the field of microscopy that has been recently used to address various inverse imaging challenges is deep learning⁹, a method of machine learning that uses an architecture of a multi-layered neural network trained to complete a specific task. Deep learning has been successfully used in microscopy for different tasks, such as denoising¹⁰, super-resolution image reconstruction^{11,12} and online optical optimization¹³, with a great impact in the field of image reconstruction^{11,14-16}.

Here, we demonstrate Deep-ROCS, a fast, label-free super-resolution microscopy method, using deep learning to combine only 6 coherent images illuminated from different angles, achieving imaging resolution beyond the diffraction limit. We report resolution improvement by a factor of 1.5 in the reconstruction of experimental ROCS data. The performance improvement of Deep-ROCS stems from the ability of neural networks to efficiently combine the speckle information of different illumination angles in the reconstruction.

2. Methods

2.1 Bead simulation for network training

To train the neural network to recover a 200 nm bead sample, we simulated two-dimensional ROCS imaging of samples with random numbers and positions of beads, within a minimal distance from the boundary Δ_{min}^{edges} , and a minimal distance between bead centers Δ_{min}^{beads} . The used light source wavelength was 405 nm and the objective lens NA was 0.7. The code ran on a standard work-station equipped with 16 GB of memory, an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 - 8700, 3.20 GHz CPU within less than 14 milliseconds. We chose the following parameters for the simulations: number of beads in the range [400, 1000], image dimensions = 256x256 pixels, bead radius of 3 pixels, $\Delta_{min}^{edges} = 3$ and $\Delta_{min}^{beads} = 5$. The steps for simulating the beads are summarized in the supplementary materials for this paper.

2.2 Filament simulation

To train the neural network to recover filaments, we implemented a computational filament generation method presented previously¹⁷. The model parameters implemented in our simulation are the following elongation step length of $\gamma = 0.2 \mu m$, number of filaments $n = 50$, colinearity parameter $\cos(\alpha) = 0.9$, mean of the normal distribution $\mu = 15 \mu m$, standard deviation of the normal distribution $\sigma = 5 \mu m$, and no centrosome or membrane were simulated.

2.3 Microscopy

To obtain coherent TIR images, a focused blue laser beam (LBX-405, Oxxius S.A., Lannion, France) is scanned using a pair of galvanometric mirrors (S-8210M, Sunny Technology, Beijing, China) along a circle in the back focal plane (BFP) of the objective lens (Plan-APO 100x 1.46 Oil DIC, Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany). In this way, the sample is subsequently illuminated by oblique plane wave from different azimuthal directions. We prepared the samples by drying a solution containing 200nm polystyrene beads (Polysciences Inc., Warrington, PA, USA) on a coverslip. Distilled water was then placed on the beads, which were attached to the coverslip due to van der Waals forces. The polar angle of incidence is chosen such that total internal reflection condition for the sample illumination is achieved (TIR-Mode). The evanescent field on the upper side of the coverslip (CS) interacts with the unlabeled

sample and the backward scattered light is collected by a CMOS camera (Grasshopper3 GS3-U3-23S6M-C, FLIR Systems Inc., Richmond, BC, Canada). To enable dark field detection, the rotating unscattered reflected beam is blocked by a diaphragm as sketched in figure 1. In dark field mode, a maximum detection NA of 1.2 can be achieved, corresponding to the maximum achievable lateral image resolution of approximately 150 nm, determined by Fourier analysis of experimental images^{4,6}. By narrowing the dark field diaphragm additionally, the detection NA can be artificially lowered, which in consequence leads to a decrease in lateral resolution⁴ (More detail in the supplementary information). This change in NA is used to validate the neural networks output image by using ROCS images of $NA \cong 1.2$ as reference for the outcome of a system with input of $NA = 0.7$. In this study we acquire a TIR-ROCS image, by adding up 72 coherent TIR images by using the galvo scanner to circulate the coherent light around the optical axis. The azimuthal angles are set to acquire 72 individual images with a uniform separation of $\phi = 5^\circ$.

2.4 Network Architecture

In case the input for the neural network is experimental data, we perform a few pre-processing steps prior to the neural network's analysis: First, we crop the images to ~ 400 images with smaller field-of-view. Next, we project the pixel values of each cropped image to be in the range $[0,1]$. We do so to give each differently illuminated image the same weight in the reconstruction process. Then, we subtract the mean pixel value from all image pixels and divide by the standard deviation of the image pixel as we found it beneficial in means of reconstruction accuracy. A more complex algorithm would use learnable weights instead of these normalization factors, that would be trained to minimize the loss function in a more optimal manner. The input to the artificial neural network is a subsample of 6 out of the 72 recorded images $p_{SD}(x, y, \phi)$ (different sized image-sets are also tested) taken from different azimuthal angles ϕ with 5° spacing, and the output is a single super-resolved image. We have decided to take 6 uniformly sampled angles: $0^\circ, 60^\circ, \dots, 300^\circ$ as they contain complementary frequency information. In the future, it may be possible to optimize the decision of which differently illuminated images to use according to the problem being solved. The neural network architecture is fully convolutional, built as an Encoder-Decoder with concatenate connections, similar to the U-net Network architecture¹⁸, with the layer composition inspired by Deep-STORM¹¹ as seen in figure 2. Before being input to the neural network, the images $p_{SD}(x, y, \phi)$ are projected to the range of $[0,1]$, and then normalized by the images mean and std. The loss function used is the L1 error:

$$L^{l_1}(p, \hat{p}, N) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |p_i(x, y, \phi) - \hat{p}_i(x, y, \phi)| \quad (4)$$

Where N is the batch size, $p_i(x, y, \phi)$ is the i^{th} reference image (ground truth) in the batch and $\hat{p}_i(x, y, \phi)$ is the matching reconstruction given as the network's output. The loss function was chosen experimentally from a set of loss functions shown to achieve superior results for image restoration¹⁹.

Figure 2: Network Architecture. We used a U-net Network architecture, with concatenate connection between layers of the same size. The input is a stack of speckle images from 6 different illumination angles and the output is a single superior-resolution image. Scale bar = 500 nm.

2.5 Network Training

The network is initially trained by using a training set of simulated images. The training dataset consists of sets of 6 low resolution images $p_{SD}(x, y, \phi, NA = 0.7)$ of different illumination angles and a single high NA ROCS image $p_{ROCS}(x, y, NA = 1.2)$ as the super-resolved reference ('ground truth'), the size of the images is 64x64 pixels, the size of the training set is 1500 images, and the validation set contains 500 images.

This initial training step on simulated data achieves excellent results when tested on simulated data (both beads and filaments (Figures. 3 and 6)); however, the simulation model does not address all the conditions of experimental data, such as unequal illumination and artifacts caused by imperfections in the illumination and imaging systems. The straightforward solution of training the network solely on experimental data is impractical, as it would require performing hundreds of ROCS experiments. In order to overcome this gap, we used the transfer learning technique²⁰, namely, we trained the network on simulated beads and then fine-tuned the network on experimental data. For this step we acquired 17 images of size 992x868 pixels and used 15 for training and 2 for testing. To augment out the effect of non-constant illumination across the FOV, we randomly crop 256x256 patches to generate 4,000 training examples, 1,600 validation examples and 1,500 test examples.

3. Results

To demonstrate the performance as well as the necessity for a deep neural network when combining coherent TIR images, we first benchmarked the neural network's performance against the current ROCS method in simulations⁴. For this benchmark we simulated a dense sample of beads $f(x, y)$ located on the same axial layer. Next, to demonstrate that using $N = 6$ illumination angles can be more beneficial, then using the sum image alone, we show here two versions of neural networks: one which only processes a single image (the sum of the 6 illumination angles) in figure 3a and 3b, and another which processes 6 images $p_{SD}(x, y, \phi)$ obtained using different illumination angles ϕ in figure 3c and 3d. As illustrated by figure 3e, the neural network that receives as input a single image $p_{ROCS}(x, y, N = 6)$ generates a decent reconstruction, however, the overlay image indicates that there is a

significant dissimilarity between the ground truth (red) and the reconstruction (blue). Additionally, according to the shift in the yellow dots (marking the center of mass of the beads) it can be seen that the sum network suffers from ROCS microscopy artifacts. The origin of these artifacts is the scattering pattern of a very dense environment, which may lead to a shift in the bead locations in ROCS images due to interferences. The input for the second network is a set of images that were illuminated from different illumination angles. As could be seen in figure 3f, the second neural network achieves a more accurate reconstruction than the neural network that receives as input a single ROCS image. The significant improvement in the quality of the reconstruction occurs thanks to the additional spatial frequency information contained in the multiple input channels, compared to their summation into one channel.

Figure 3: Simulated beads. (a) A single ROCS image, calculated by summing the images of simulated beads over all angles, is fed into a neural network (b) that outputs a high-resolution reconstruction. (c) 6 speckle images captured while illuminating the sample from 6 different illumination directions are fed into a related neural network (d) that outputs a single high-resolution reconstruction. (e) Left: sum network reconstruction; Right: zoom in to a ROI and overlay image between the ground truth (red) and the reconstruction (blue), white areas indicate similarity (overlap) between the images. The yellow dots mark the bead centers used for the ground truth image. (f) Left: 6 illumination-angles-network reconstruction; Right: zoom in to a ROI and overlay image. All scale bars = 500 nm.

Furthermore, to compare quantitatively the accuracy of each approach, we used multi-scale structured similarity index measure (MS-SSIM)²¹ as our similarity measure between the ground truth images and reconstructed images. The structured similarity index measure (SSIM) of a single patch is defined in equation (5):

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (5)$$

Where: x, y are the reconstructed image and the ground truth image respectively, μ_x, μ_y are the average intensities of the images, σ_x, σ_y are the standard deviations of the image intensities, σ_{xy} is the covariance of x and y , and c_1, c_2 are constant values to stabilize the division with small denominator values. As could be seen in equation (5), when $\mu_x = \mu_y$ and $\sigma_x = \sigma_y = \sigma_{xy}$ the SSIM score would be 1. The lower bound for this measure is 0 as all the parameters are non-negative. One drawback of SSIM is the fact that it focuses mostly on global parameters of the entire image and therefore is not indicative of local differences in an image, which are very important in our case. To overcome the locality limitation, we use MS-SSIM, which is an

extension of SSIM that calculates the similarity measure between the reconstructed image and the ground truth over several patches of different sizes. This change enables the MS-SSIM to observe local differences between two images, namely, to indicate whether the reconstructed image is similar to the ground truth in more local scale. The MS-SSIM scores obtained on this benchmark were: 0.18 for ROCS, 0.31 for the sum network and 0.81 for 6 illumination angles network. The MS-SSIM scores indicates that both neural networks have generated more accurate reconstructions than ROCS reconstruction, however, the sum network was significantly less accurate than the 6 illumination angles network. This suggests that the information in the individual illumination angles is vital, and therefore should be fully exploited.

Next, we tested the network on experimental data. The data was taken with an NA = 0.7 objective. We used the ROCS sum image acquired with a higher NA of 1.2 as the ground truth image. The results seen in figure 4 suggest that Deep-ROCS can recover a denoised version of the underlying beads image more accurately than standard ROCS microscopy. Quantitatively, the mean MS-SSIM score over 1500 test images is 0.81 for ROCS and 0.88 for the neural network.

Figure 4: Experimental bead data. (a) ROCS image combining 72 different illumination angles with NA = 0.7; Scale bar = 1 μm . (b) ROCS image combining 6 different illumination angles with NA = 0.7 (c) Ground truth ROCS image with NA = 1.2. (d) Deep-ROCS reconstruction image. The second row contains zoom in to a ROI. Scale bar = 250 nm.

As could be seen in figure 4, the neural network successfully reconstructs an image with ~ 1.5 times higher NA, namely, it reconstructs images with a resolution corresponding to NA = 1.2 from 6 different images captured with a lower NA of 0.7. Since image resolution scales with the NA, we effectively increase the output image resolution by a factor of ~ 1.5 . This result is consistent with frequency coverage analysis²² (see “Resolution quantification” section in the supplementary information). Instead of summing the information across different images (as in eq. 2), Deep-ROCS applies an optimized function f_{deep} to provide resolution improvement, which can be described by:

$$p_{SD}(x, y, NA = 0.7) = f_{deep}(|E_{cam}(x, y, \phi_1, NA = 0.7)|^2, \dots, |E_{cam}(x, y, \phi_6, NA = 0.7)|^2) \approx p_{ROCS}(x, y, NA = 1.2) \quad (6)$$

Increasing the number of speckle pattern images taken per FOV results in longer acquisition time, limiting temporal resolution. Therefore, we wish to decrease the required number of speckle pattern images per FOV; however, this is expected to decrease the reconstruction quality of Deep ROCS. Therefore, it is important to quantify the performance of Deep ROCS as a function of the number of illumination angles N per sample to understand the spatio-temporal resolution tradeoff. For this purpose, we have trained seven different networks on the same data, using 72, 36, 24, 12, 6, 3 and 2 different illumination angles. The MS-SSIM

accuracy for each experiment is presented in figure 5. In this work we chose the nominal number of illumination angles of Deep-ROCS to be six, which exhibits a good compromise between acquisition time and reconstruction performance.

Figure 5: Comparison between ROCS (blue) and Deep-ROCS (orange) MS-SSIM scores using different number of experimentally measured illumination angles as input. Each dot indicates the number of subsamples taken from the entire set of illumination angle data. The subsampled directions are uniformly distributed from 0-360 to generate a circular view of the sample. The MS-SSIM score was calculated over 1500 experimental images.

Finally, to demonstrate the applicability of our method on more complex samples, e.g. biological structures, we tested Deep-ROCS on simulated filaments, as detailed in section 2.2. The results are presented in figure 6.

As expected, highly bended filaments with a diameter of 30 nm pose a more significant challenge than 200 nm beads. Nevertheless, the reconstructed images of Deep-ROCS reveal significant spatial information, resolving the overall structure of the filament sample. According to the simulations, conventional ROCS image formation seems to work better for circular objects such as beads, than for filament networks. Deep-ROCS, on the other hand, maintains high reconstruction accuracy for both types of objects.

Figure 6: Simulated filaments. (a) Example imaged speckle patterns, corresponding to illuminations from three different angles $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 60^\circ$ and $\phi = 120^\circ$. Scale bar = 600 nm. (b) ROCS image calculated by summing the filament images over all illumination angles ($N=72$), (c) The ground truth image (d) The output of Deep-ROCS using $N=6$ different illumination angles. Scale bar = 600 nm. The third row contains zoom-ins to a ROI corresponding to the second-row images. Scale bar = 100 nm.

4. Discussion

In this paper we have presented Deep-ROCS, a novel method utilizing a deep neural network to obtain high-quality images from only six coherent low-resolution images full of speckles. Although conventional label-free superior resolution images from rotating coherent scattering (ROCS) microscopy can be acquired within 10 ms, they do not combine the acquired high-spatial-frequency content efficiently. For more efficient incorporation of high-frequency information, access to single direction images is necessary. However, the acquisition of $N = 36$ images would slow down the high throughput of ROCS by a factor of 36 (not limited by the number of coherent photons). A way out of the classical dilemma between optimizing spatial and temporal resolution is the Deep-ROCS concept. We have shown that Deep-ROCS is a fast and robust solution for extracting high spatial frequency content encoded in the differently illuminated images.

We could show by simulations and experiments that Deep-ROCS significantly improves the spatial resolution of conventional ROCS imaging at moderate numerical apertures ($NA < 1$), and this resolution improvement could be achieved with only six illumination angles. The performance of Deep-ROCS was illustrated by different distributions of 200 nm beads: Deep-

ROCS using 6 angles images achieved a MS-SSIM score of 0.88, which is higher than the MS-SSIM score of 0.81 for conventional ROCS imaging (approximated by summing up 72 speckle pattern images).

We further demonstrate the potential of Deep-ROCS to reconstruct more complex structures as filaments. We calculated the mean MS-SSIM score over 1500 simulated filament images and showed that Deep-ROCS outperformed ROCS with a major improvement in the MS-SSIM score. While the mean reconstruction score for ROCS was approximately 0.48, Deep-ROCS mean score was 0.85. The quality differences are clearly seen in figure 6.

The idea of Fourier plane sampling extension has been demonstrated in other techniques such as in Structured Illuminated microscopy (SIM)⁷ and Fourier Ptychography microscopy (FPM)²³. Deep learning solutions combined with FPM enabled researchers to generate high-resolution images of large fields of view²⁴ from a sequence of low resolution images. While increasing the field-of-view relies on a low NA objective lens, here we focus on super-resolution microscopy using high NA objective lenses and laser illumination. Another important property of Deep-ROCS is its rapid inference time of approximately 10 ms for image reconstruction. This property enables potential real-time super-resolution imaging. To facilitate faster acquisition, one may use an Acousto-Optical Modulator (AOM) or another form of laser switching, to allow the combination of fast rotation with individual angle acquisition.

In summary, Deep-ROCS is a strong tool that obtains label free superior-resolution images from rotating coherent scattering experiments, with inference time of a few milli-seconds and improved reconstruction accuracy over standard ROCS. Future directions include generalization of the neural network to other structures – namely, increase the flexibility of the method by enriching the training set to include various models beyond beads or filaments.

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Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) file for supporting content.

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